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GARCH MODELLING OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN SELECTED CITIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined GARCH modelling of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria. It aimed at building a suitable GARCH Model of Covid-19 Pandemic between the National Weekly Confirmed cases (NWC) in Lagos and Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. This study used a secondary statistical data extracted from the website of the National Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) on the daily and weekly reported and confirmed cases of Covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria from March 16th, 2020 to May 9th, 2021. The Gretl 18 and Minitab 17 programmes were used to obtain the parameters that constitute the GARCH model, the AIC, BIC, LHC, HQC, R2, R2-Adjusted, SSE and MSE. The result from the comparison of the two models; GARCH(0,1) of FCT and GARCH(1,0) of Lagos showed that GARCH(1,0) was better, considering the model selection criteria (AIB,BIC,HQC and LKH) and parameter estimates (p-values). This study was able to establish that the Lagos GARCH(1,0) was the best model that describes the data. It was recommended that there should be adequate monitoring in Lagos state to contain the spread of the virus and also, policy makers should put in place a better health care policy favourable to all.

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